

An Investigation of the Role of Neuro-Linguistic Programming in Iranian EFL Classes

Hamid Gholami^{1,*} - Sara Kamkar² - Samira Golshani³

¹Department of ELT, Kermanshah Branch, Islamic Azad University, Kermanshah, Iran.

²Department of ELT, Kermanshah Branch, Islamic Azad University, Kermanshah, Iran.

³Department of ELT, Kermanshah Branch, Islamic Azad University, Kermanshah, Iran.

ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to examine the Neuro-Linguistic programming (NLP) techniques applied in Iranian EFL classes and show the possible relationship between NLP techniques used by teachers and the students' satisfaction. An NLP's questionnaire was administrated based on NLP's techniques to clarify the techniques employed in the Iranian EFL classes. An additional questionnaire was used to assess the students' satisfaction. A Pearson correlation test was conducted to determine the relationship between teachers' use of NLP techniques and students' satisfaction. The result of the study revealed that building rapport was the most frequent technique in Iranian EFL classes. Furthermore, a significant relationship between NLP's techniques and students' satisfaction was obtained.

Keywords: Neuro-Linguistic programming, Iranian EFL classes, students' satisfaction

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, education has changed dramatically. Several research in education, psychology and the neurosciences have tried to shed light on effective learning (e.g., [1]). Language learners learn differently and this variability arises from cognitive, social and linguistic factors. Teachers and researchers follow to come up with techniques and strategies to increase their student's motivation and change their attitude toward learning a foreign language besides using some traditional methods. Neuro-Linguistic Programming (NLP) was introduced and developed by Richard Bandler and John Grinder in the mid-1970s as a therapy helping to attain high performance in learning [2]. As the name implies, it derives from the three scopes; neurology, linguistic and programming. In NLP, the trainer should focus on how learners experience the world. It explains how body and mind are interconnected and also operate with the idea that unconscious mind is more efficient than the conscious one in control of behavior [3].

[4] were the pioneers in bringing NLP into ELT in the late 1990s. NLP's activities enhance learning, increase motivation, boost remembering and incorporate raising of sensory awareness with language learning [3]. [4] state that NLP has two main parts, presupposition and the core concept. Presupposition forms belief and attitude about learning and includes some principles. On the other hand, the core concept is called the heart of NLP [2] and includes four pillars: outcomes, rapport, sensory acuity, flexibility that accompany by representational systems (VAKOG), eye movements, anchoring, metaprogramming and modelling.

According to NLP, every individual differs physically and is different in their experiences and thinking styles. It also states that we can learn from others experiences due to the similarities in our nervous systems [3]. Thus, NLP is a programme that can be adapted to all types of learners and is a suitable technique for English classes. [4] stated that NLP is a collection of techniques, patterns, and strategies for better effective communication, personal growth, and learning. NLP has several similarities and differences with learning theories. The first learning theory is behaviorism working on classical conditioning that provided the base for modern developmental psychology. Unlike behaviorist that emphasizes learning and remembering by reinforcement, NLP reinforcement is not considered a base of anchor. Anchoring in NLP is defined as consciously induced stimulus-response conditioning.

According to [5], in NLP, a stimulus is linked to and triggers a physiological state called an anchor. NLP also has some common features with Piaget's constructivist approach that focuses on learning as a search for

meaning, and requires understanding the whole as well as parts [6], on the other hand, NLP's meta-programme has chunking-up that means to gain a whole overview of a certain topic and chunking down consider details and understanding parts of the whole [7]. NLP also has some common featured with Bandura's Social Learning Theory that combines learning principle with cognitive process with the effect of observational learning [8]. Techniques such as goal setting and self-reinforcement are used to help people acquire the characteristics of a competent role mode in this theory [9]. NLP has many similar aspects such as modelling to modify behavior, visualization to alter mental states and behavioral anchoring technique that employs both stimulus and reinforcement.

Iranian educational system is based on the traditional method of learning and teaching. ELT in Iran has been widely influenced by behaviorism. Behaviorism ignores the role of learners and their cognitive or mental process. Also, it does not consider unconscious mind's influence on behavior and instead focuses on external observable behavior [10]. Moreover, the teaching orthodoxy in Iranian EFL context rarely gives an appropriate place to the affective domain, which is as significant as the other domain if not more. Although there have been a lot of studies on the impact of difference techniques on enhancing learning, only scant attention has been paid to studies examined the role of NLP as humanistic approaches in EFL classes. The present study aims to examine the neuro-linguistic programming techniques in Iranian EFL classes and to examine the potential relationship between NLP techniques, used by teachers and the students' satisfaction.

The NLP is concerned with the uniqueness of every individual. In NLP, the classroom is a place where individuality can be fostered, so NLP tries to use various tasks which motivate students to express themselves through the foreign language. This research can be fruitful since it will study whether teachers use NLP in their classes or not. Another critical concept considered in teaching by NLP is the emotion of learners. This study focuses on whether emotions and feelings that learners need for learning are taken care of by their Iranian teachers. Emotion creates the sense of belonging to the communication, so this research investigates the extent to which students' affective factors are considered in EFL classes, and whether using NLP correlates with students' satisfaction, which is a key factor in their motivation.

To achieve the purpose of the study, the following research questions were proposed:

1. What techniques of NLP are more applied in Iranian EFL class?
2. Is there any relationship between teacher's use of NLP techniques and the student's satisfaction?

2. METHODS

2.1 Design

This study is both qualitative and quantitative. It is ex post facto in design since it does not include any treatment and the subjects are not randomly assigned - they are categorized based on a particular characteristic. Because the questionnaires are interpreted using an inferential statistic, it is a quantitative study.

2.2 Participants

Two groups participated in this study. Thirty female and male teachers (N=30) majoring in English teaching, English literature, and English translation working in different institutes in Kermanshah and also their students were observed. The teacher had a variety of teaching experiences and they were instructing learners with different proficiency levels and an age range of 16 to 30 years old. A hundred and forty learners (N = 140) were in beginner, elementary and intermediate levels, based on the institute hierarchy.

2.3 Instruments

Two types of questionnaires were employed in this research. First, the NLP questionnaire (Appendix A), intended to measure teachers' use of NLP in the classroom, designed and validated by Pishghadam, Shayesteh, and Shapori (2001). This questionnaire comprised of 38 items with five scales with possible answers from (5) "always" to (1) "never". This questionnaire includes eight factors of NLP: flexibility, anchoring, elicitation, modeling, individual difference, and rapport, emotional and cognitive boosters [11]. The second questionnaire was "The teacher Confirmation Scale" (Appendix B) designed and validated by [12] and was employed to investigate the relationship between teachers' behavior and satisfactions of the learners. This questionnaire included of 16 items and three parts: responding to questions, demonstrating interest, and teaching style that range from (1) "strongly disagree" to (5) "strongly agree" that show the role of behaviors and style of teachers in the classroom.

2.4 Procedures

This study was carried out in 5 different institutes in Kermanshah. Thirty female and male teachers and 140 students were observed during three weeks. The first questionnaire was the NLP questionnaire filled by the researcher as the observer and teachers. The second was “The teacher Confirmation Scale” filled by students. The researcher observed each teacher’s classroom for three sessions and based on their observations, she filled the questionnaire including items to evaluate the teacher’s use of NLP techniques. Then, the teachers were asked to answer the questions in 20 minutes. Total score of the questionnaire filled by the teacher and the observer was divided by two and the mean was considered as the end outcome. If a teacher used one of the techniques just once during the three sessions, then he would get two at that item if twice then three if three times then four if he had used the techniques more than four times, then five would have been assigned. Students were asked to fill in the second questionnaire with answer ranging from (1) “strongly disagree” to (5) “strongly agree”. The total score of each questionnaire was calculated based on the students’ responses.

2.5 Data Analysis

To achieve the goal of the study, data was collected by two instruments, NLP questionnaire and the teacher Confirmation Scale, over five weeks. Then the result of teacher Confirmation Scale and NLP scale were correlated using Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (PPMCC) on SPSS software to find the potential relation between teacher’s behavior and student’s satisfaction.

3. RESULT

3.1 Addressing the First Research Question

Based on the questionnaire, the following findings were obtained; the maximum average belongs to the first item “She/he shows her/his interest to the topics presented by her/his students?”, other practices were also popular including: item 2 “In answering the questions, she/he give hints to the students”, and 3 “While teaching, she/he uses some of the words or phrases used by the learners” ($\bar{X}=23.2$), item 13 “She/he creates new challenges for her/his students” and 30 “She/he write down the new subject material on the board as a model” ($\bar{X}=23$), item 9 “To ensure learners’ understanding and to remove the ambiguities, she/he asks them some questions” and 32 “She/he gives feedback to their student’s correct and incorrect answers” ($\bar{X}=21.8$), item 11 “She/he gives enough time to the language learners to write down notes and do class activities” and 28 “She/he get her/his students’ ideas of the topics presented in the class” ($\bar{X}=21$), on the other hand some items including 35 “She/he asks successful language learners to talk about their personal ways of progress in the classroom” and 36 “She/he expect her/his students to adjust themselves to her/his teaching rate” ($\bar{X}=15.2$) were reported to be the least popular items.

Table 1. Descriptive statistic of NLP’s techniques

N	Minimum	Maximum
38	9.00	27.20

3.2 Addressing the Second Research Question

To investigate the relation between teacher’s use of NLP techniques and the student’s satisfactions, two questionnaires were used. An NLP questionnaire and the teacher confirmation scale. Each option of the items was given a value from one to five, so the average score was used to calculate the total score of every class. Therefore, each class had a certain score that was compared with number of teacher’s observations. Then the score of NLP questionnaire and teacher confirmation scale were calculated in SPSS.

Table 2. Correlation between the use of NLP’s techniques and students’ satisfaction

		VAR0001	VAR0002
VAR0001	Pearson correlation	1	.361
	Sig.(2-tailed)		.0164
	N	30	30
VAR0001	Pearson correlation	.361	1
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.0164	
	N	30	30

The obtained data gained from Pearson product-moment correlation in Table 2 indicated that the significance level was .0165. Thus, it can be inferred that there is a meaningful correlation between the use of NLP techniques and students' satisfaction ($P < .05$).

4. DISCUSSION

This study dealt with the different techniques of NLP used in Iranian EFL classes and their effect on students' satisfaction. According to the results of this study, which were derived from the analysis of two questionnaires, it seems that Iranian teachers use many NLP techniques. This study considered the factors like anchoring, modelling, rapport, individual differences, eyes movement, emotion and motivation. Recent studies on using NLP techniques in education in general [3] and [12] have suggested that some NLP techniques can lead to improved performance in English language teaching and learning.

Rapport is one of the techniques used by Iranian teachers. Rapport has a significant role in communication between teachers and learners, decreasing their anxiety and boosting their self-confidence. [13] agreed with the role of rapport he had researched NLP and pronunciation. He stated that rapport is a critical priority in NLP, and it is conducive to success in pronunciation learning. He also explains rapport as meta-communication that can be defined as a desire to constantly suggest internal representational, leading someone to a facultative state. Thus, the way the teachers talk about acquiring good pronunciation and the message sent consciously or subconsciously to students include significant suggestive communicative patterns, so NLP help to use language more efficiently.

Another technique mentioned in the NLP's questionnaire was modelling, Iranian EFL teachers usually try to be good models of language learning. They try to give their students some hints on learning a new language. More specifically, modelling enhances learners study skills and goal setting techniques. [14] intending to help students improve their spelling by using the NLP spelling strategy, carried out her research with a group of Emirati male students at the college where she worked. [14] suggests that teachers should first find out their students' preferred learning styles, which can be done by asking them to spell words and observing their eye movements; or by using learning style questionnaires to focus on their behavior and preferences. She showed that people who are good at spelling use three main Spelling strategies that combine the three main sensory channels: visual, auditory, and kinesthetic.

Taking the principle of modelling in NLP as a basis, [15] in his research explore whether or not NLP modelling works in essay writing. He stated that NLP modelling enables students to learn better by identifying and replicating the internal processing strategies used by a person who successfully masters spelling, negotiating, and pronouncing correctly. [15] concludes that the teacher should play the role of a facilitator in the implementation process of the framework. [16] explored the relationship between NLP and the on-going motivation of students throughout their undergraduate process of writing theses. The study focused on the NLP framework for goal setting, time management and motivation. The data analysis comprised student responses to surveys and interviews showed that the use of NLP strategies improved the self-efficacy of students who were carrying out their undergraduate dissertation.

5. CONCLUSION

The present study was set up to determine the impact of NLP on learning a second language, investigate how much of NLP's methods are used by teachers in Iranian EFL classes, and investigate the relationship between applying NLP's method and students' satisfaction. As a finding in the present study, the technique used most frequently by teachers in Iranian EFL class was the first one "She/he shows her/his interest to the topics presented by her/his students?" so the average item of this question revealed that the Iranian teachers broadly apply rapport that is the heart of NLP in their class, it supports [17] idea about rapport that teachers try to maintain better attraction and involvement in the learner by showing their interest in the proposed topic and their ideas. It is a state of harmony that enables people to have excellent communication ability [18], find similarities, and enjoy relationships.

The lowest score is related to the tenth question, "She/he let the learners move freely in the classroom". This question shows that there is no paying attention to individual differences because regarding the representational system, different people learn differently, Kinesthetic people, unlike other people-auditory and visual- learn through movement, usually get information through their hands or bodies or emotion, and they like to touch things, move their hands and feet. The score of this question showed the kinesthetic learners are sometimes ignored in EFL classes in Iran. The second question of this study was the relationship between

applying NLP's techniques and students' satisfaction. The calculation of the score obtained by Pearson-product-moment showed a significant relationship between the two variables. Therefore the results from the present research shed light on the fact that although the different method of NLP is unconsciously used in EFL Iranian class, using this method has a significant effect on the satisfaction of learners.

The study results make the teachers aware of the importance of their behavior on second language learners' satisfaction. It is assumed that NLP's methods and techniques are used unconsciously in teaching language in Iran. They are considered interesting, engaging, and motivating, so NLP is a good option if a teacher knows its principles. Neuro-linguistic Programming is not just a teaching language method. This is a humanistic training philosophy that includes several techniques. It is related to humanistic principles and communication activities that have been used and proven successful in language teaching. Essentially, NLP is one way to become the best teacher. Therefore, teaching through NLP is a process of creating states that encourage learning, and facilitating learners' investigation, enhancing their internal representations, and helping the learners lead towards the desired goal or outcome. According to [19], the most critical implications of NLP in language classrooms are giving the students positive messages rather than negative ones, helping the students believe that they can learn, and building self-esteem in the teacher and the students as learners. With the techniques of NLP, students pay more attention to the words they do understand rather than the words they do not understand. It inspires students to think about their learning environments and techniques that are suitable for them, improves classroom behavior and gains more active pupil engagement, particularly in whole-class discussion and individual learning.

REFERENCES

- [1] Yorio, C. (1981). Teaching methods, the brain and other simple matters or " Are we ready for applied neurolinguistics?". *Toronto Working Papers in Linguistics*, 2.
- [2] Richard, J, C., & Rodgers, T. (2001). Approaches and methods in language teaching. United State: Cambridge university press.
- [3] O'Connor, J., & Seymour, J. (1990). Introducing Neuro-Linguistic Programming: Psychology skills for influencing people. London: Aquarian/Thorsons
- [4] Norman, S., & Revell, J. (1999). Handing over: NLP-based activities for language learning. Great Britain: Saffire Press
- [5] Rosenberg, M. (2008). NLP in BE: Marjorie Rosenberg finds a place for Neurolinguistic programming in the business English classroom. *English Teaching Professional* 56, 34(2), 5. Retrieved from Google Scholar database.
- [6] Korthagen, F. A. J. (2004). In search of the essence of a good teacher: Towards a more holistic approach in teacher education. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 20(1), 77-97. Retrieved from Google Scholar database.
- [7] Dilts, R. & DeLozier, J. (2000). Meta-programs: Chunking-up and chunking down. In *Encyclopedia of Systemic NLP and NLP New Coding*. Scotts Valley: NLP University Press.
- [8] Ashford, J. & LeCroy, C. (2010). Human behavior in the social environment: A multidimensional Perspective. Canada: Nelson education Ltd
- [9] Peel, D. (2005). The significance of behavioral learning theory to the development of effective coaching practice. *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring*, 3(1), 18-29.
- [10] McLeod, S. A. (2013). Behaviorist approach retrieved from <http://www.simply psychology .org/behaviorism.html>.
- [11] Pishghadam, R., Shapoori, M., & Shayesteh, S. (2011). NLP and its relationship with teacher success, gender, teaching experience, and degree: A comparative study. *World journal of English language*, 1(2), p2.
- [12] Revell, J. and Norman, S. (1999) Handling over: NLP Based Activities for Language Learning. London: Saffire Press.
- [13] Hismanglu, M. (2006). Current perspective on pronunciation learning and teaching. *Journal of language and linguistic studies*, 2(1), 101-110.
- [14] Hamilton, R. (2008). The NLP spelling strategy. *Humanising Language Teaching*, 5(1). Retrieved from <http://www.hltmag.co.uk/jan03/sart2.htm>.
- [15] Tosey, P. (2008). 'It's a living thing': A neuro-linguistic programming perspective on essay writing. *Humanising Language Teaching*, 10(5). Retrieved from <http://www.hltmag .co.uk/oct08/mart02.htm>

- [16] Skinner, H., & Croft, R. (2009). Neuro-linguistic programming techniques to improve the self-efficacy of undergraduate dissertation students. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 1(1), 29-38. Retrieved from www.NLPresearch.org
- [17] Bandler, R., & Grinder, J. (1975). *The structure of magic I*. California: Science and Behavior Books, Inc
- [18] Revell, J., & Norman, S. (1997). *In your hands: NLP in ELT*. Saffire Press.
- [19] Tosey, P., & Mathison, J. (2003). Neuro-linguistic programming and learning theory: a response. *The Curriculum Journal*, 14(3), 371-388.

Appendix A

Neuro-linguistic Programming Questionnaire

Neuro-linguistic Programming Questionnaire

1. Never 2. Rarely 3. Occasionally 4. Frequently 5. Always

1. She/he shows her/his interest to the topics presented by her/his students.
2. In answering the questions, she/he give hints to the students.
3. While teaching, she/he uses some of the words or phrases used by the learners.
4. She/he help her/his students with less ability.
5. When the learners do not understand something, she/he presents it in a new way.
6. She/he ask her/his students to pay attention to similarities and differences of the subjects.
7. She/he give her/his students the words needed for a conversation.
8. She/he pay attention to the language learners' eye movements.
9. To ensure learners' understanding and to remove the ambiguities, she/he asks them some questions.
10. She/he let the learners move freely in the classroom.
11. She/he give enough time to the language learners to write down notes and do class activities.
12. She/he tries to create a positive feeling in her/his students toward language learning.
13. She/he creates new challenges for her/his students.
14. When the language learners do not understand a subject matter, she/he writes it down on the board.
15. If needed, she/he ask the language learners to speak clearly.
16. For holding a dialogue, she/he presents the required grammar.
17. She/he prefers to call her/his students by their first name.
18. She/he welcome new and creative answers.
19. She/he make uses of flash cards, CDs, posters, and other teaching aids.
20. She/he asks her/his students to pay attention to details.
21. She/he pay attentions to individual differences.

22. She/he talks about herself/ himself and her/his own experiences in the classroom.
23. She/he asks her/his students of her/his teaching and speaking rate in the classroom.
24. She/he makes use of only one teaching method.
25. She/he assign a special duty for every individual.
26. During the teaching process, she/he writes down the new material on the board.
27. All her/his students' opinions are important to her/his.
28. She/he get her/his students' ideas of the topics presented in the class.
29. For better learning and understanding, she/he asks the learners to take notes.
30. She/he write down the new subject material on the board as a model.
31. She/he inform her/his students of their progress.
32. She/he gives feedback to her/his students' correct and incorrect answers.
33. She/he runs the class in a formal way.
34. She/he correct all the language learners' errors.
35. She/he asks successful language learners to talk about their personal ways of progress in the classroom.
36. She/he expect my students to adjust themselves to her/his teaching rate.
37. The learners can form groups freely.
38. She/he doesn't make use of encouragement for her/his students' progress.

